

COMPLEX ECHOGRAPHIC SIGNS OF GLOMERULONEPHRITIS IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE AND CHRONIC COURSE

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that according to the World Health Organization, diseases of the urinary system currently occupy the 2nd place among the main pathologies in children. Over the past decade, the incidence of kidney diseases in children has increased by 2.5-3 times and, depending on the region, reaches from 20.6 to 106 cases per 1000 children per year. One of the pathologies of the urinary system in children is glomerulonephritis, which is a large group of immune-inflammatory diseases that mainly affect the glomerular apparatus of the kidneys. Despite the complexity of different forms of the disease, the general result of its development to a certain stage is renal fibrosis, which includes glomerular sclerosis, tubular atrophy, interstitial fibrosis and changes in the vascular network of the kidneys. Early detection of fibrosis in kidney diseases in children is important for preventing the development of chronic renal failure. Chronic glomerulonephritis is often detected at the stage of significant and irreversible kidney damage with the development of nephrosclerosis. In such cases, the opportunity for timely diagnosis and treatment is missed, which could prevent the development of the pathological process in the kidneys, but information on this issue is limited.*

Definitely, a number of scientific studies are being conducted around the world aimed at improving the methods of early diagnosis and treatment of glomerulonephritis in children, as well as reducing the number of relapses. In this area, it is advisable to use non-ionizing safe diagnostic methods when examining children with this disease.

In standard diagnostic methods, multiparameter ultrasound (gray-scale, Doppler, elastography), excretory urography and radionuclide scintigraphy are widely used. However, due to allergic reactions to contrast agents and significant negative effects of the radiation dose during X-ray and radiological studies, the use of these methods in children is limited. In such cases, the use of complex technologies, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), provides additional opportunities for accurate and reliable diagnostics. In this regard, there is a growing need to search for methods that allow early detection of glomerulonephritis in children, including further development and improvement of non-ionizing methods and detailed analysis of long-term results, which is of particular importance for solving many unresolved issues.

Keywords: *pulsatility, glomerulonephritis, chronic PIGN, C-reactive protein, radiation dose.*

Objective of the study. To study the complex echo graphic signs of glomerulonephritis in children with acute and chronic course.

Material and methods of the study. The research presents the results of a study of 220 children with glomerulonephritis, of which 160 children with glomerulonephritis formed the main group and 60 practically healthy children were included in the control group (without signs of inflammatory kidney diseases).

The study consisted of two stages. First, outpatient cards and medical histories of all children with GN treated from 2020 to 2023 impatiently at the Children's National Medical Center in the nephrology department of the Department of Medical Radiology were analyzed.

The clinical, functional status of patients, data from anamnestic and laboratory-instrumental studies were examined. Then, at the second stage, clinical, standard general clinical laboratory and biochemical studies, a comprehensive ultrasound of the kidneys using shear wave elastography were carried out. If necessary, an MRI was done.

Depending on the results, the children were divided into two groups - "Chronic GN" and "Acute GN". Patients in whom clinical manifestations of the disease disappeared, urine and blood parameters were restored, were in the group of children with acute PIGN. Their number was 64 people. Patients with clinical and laboratory changes were assigned to the group with chronic PIGN. There were 96 of them. In total, there were 92 boys (57.5%) and 68 girls (42.5%) from 3 months to 18 years.

Results of the study. In both groups of children, a connection was found between the post-infectious state, mainly with acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI) and / or oropharyngeal infections. Skin lesions in the form of ulcers were found in patients from the CGN group. Recurrent furunculosis was observed in two children, and acne (folliculitis) on the face was identified in two adolescents.

Moreover, the analysis of clinical data shows that at the initial stage of the disease, there were no statistically significant differences in the frequency of clinical symptoms and syndromes depending on the form of the disease (acute or chronic).

During the analysis of biochemical parameters, some statistically significant differences were revealed between the groups of patients, depending on the nature of the course of glomerulonephritis (GN). The level of C-reactive protein at the time of the first hospitalization was significantly higher in children with acute GN.

However, a year later, at the time of the second hospitalization, this indicator was higher in the group of patients with chronic GN. Patients with chronic glomerulonephritis had higher levels of urea and creatinine in the serum (1.5 and 1.8 times, respectively), compared with the corresponding indicators in patients with acute glomerulonephritis, during rehospitalization.

Definitely, the results of urine analysis play a key role in assessing the laboratory status of patients with glomerulonephritis. They indicate more pronounced hematuria in children with chronic glomerulonephritis both in the initial period of the disease and a year after its onset.

Certainly, a decrease in creatinine excretion, glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and urine specific gravity is also noted against the background of increased proteinuria in the same patients a year later during repeated hospitalizations. Of the 64 examined children with acute glomerulonephritis, 35 (81.9%) had nephrotic syndrome and 29 (18.1%) had hematuric syndrome. While distributing children by stages of chronic glomerulonephritis: the active stage was diagnosed in 66 (68.7%) cases, compared with the remission stage in 30 (31.3%).

Additionally, the characteristics of the echographic image of chronic glomerulonephritis correlated with the phase and duration of the disease. In children, at the initial stages of exacerbation, a slight increase in kidney volume and a slight increase in parenchyma echogenicity were observed.

During the remission period, the ultrasound image of the kidneys may be normal. As the disease progresses, a symmetrical decrease in kidney volume is observed, and the echogenicity of

the parenchyma becomes constantly increased. At the stage of decompensation of chronic glomerulonephritis, the kidneys decrease in size, are poorly detected against the background of surrounding tissues, with uniform thinning of the parenchyma.

Besides that, at the stage of decompensation of chronic glomerulonephritis, the ultrasound picture is characterized by a symmetrical decrease in the size of the kidneys in dynamics.

In the terminal stage of the disease, the kidney sizes become smaller than normal, and cortical echogenicity increases. Of the examined children, 19 had nephrotic syndrome. The echographic signs of the developed nephrotic syndrome were the following changes:

Characteristics of the ultrasound picture include:

- significant increase in kidney size.
- increased resistance index.
- marked thickening of the parenchyma (more than 2.2 cm).
- thickening of the cortex, especially the columns, with increased echogenicity.
- enlargement of the pyramids, taking a triangular shape.
- increased corticomedullary differentiation.
- compression of the renal sinus.

It is clear that fluid retention is manifested by its presence in the pleural cavities, pericardium, as well as ascites, an increase in the minute volume of blood circulation and perirenal effusion.

It should be mentioned that in children with chronic glomerulonephritis, the following is noted in the color Doppler mapping mode of ultrasound examination of the kidneys: asymmetry of hemodynamic parameters; diffuse depletion of the intrarenal vascular pattern due to a decrease or absence of small branches of segmental arteries; blood flow turbulence; localization of rare, thinned and deformed vessels ($p < 0.001$).

The studies have shown that in children in the active stage of chronic inflammatory kidney disease (CIKD), intrarenal hemodynamics differs significantly from children in the control group. In particular, more pronounced violations of Color Doppler mapping (CDM) parameters are noted, such as:

- blood flow turbulence (31.3%).
- asymmetry of hemodynamic parameters (34.4%).
- location of rare, thinned and deformed vessels (6.3%).
- diffuse depletion of vascularization (31.3%).

Moreover, Pulse Doppler showed disturbances of renal hemodynamics in the active stage of chronic glomerulonephritis (CG). The most preserved blood flow was observed in patients with the active stage of CG, having a nephrotic form.

It is not a secret, in patients with the nephrotic form of CG, pronounced disturbances of renal hemodynamics were revealed, manifested by a significant decrease in vascular resistance at the level of the arcuate artery. In the active stage of CGN in children, in the pulse-wave mode, resistance in large vessels was not disturbed, but starting from the interlobar artery, they decreased, the arcuate artery reached the lowest level.

The resistance index Ri (normal 0.6-0.7) was 0.72 ± 0.04 in the renal artery trunk, 0.65 ± 0.06 in the segmental artery, 0.60 ± 0.04 in the interlobar arteries and 0.53 ± 0.04 in the arcuate artery. The pulsator index Pi (normal 1.0-1.5) was 1.47 ± 0.15 in the renal artery trunk, 1.22 ± 0.18 in the segmental artery, 1.00 ± 0.10 in the interlobar arteries and 0.85 ± 0.06 in the arcuate artery. The

pulsatory index S/D (normal 2.5-3.5) was 3.52 ± 0.39 in the renal artery trunk, 3.08 ± 0.39 in the segmental artery, 2.41 ± 0.27 in the interlobar arteries, and 2.24 ± 0.14 in the arcuate artery.

Statistically significant differences in systolic blood flow velocity (Vs) were found between the control group (20.6 ± 0.5 mm/sec and 17.6 ± 0.5 mm/sec, respectively, $p < 0.001$). As chronic kidney disease progressed, an additional decrease in the value was noted. In patients with active chronic glomerulonephritis (CG), there is a violation of intrarenal hemodynamics, manifested by a significant decrease in diastolic blood flow velocity (Vd): 7.6 ± 0.12 mm / sec compared to the control group, where Vd is 9.24 ± 0.28 mm / sec; respectively, $p < 0.05$. While analyzing the values of the resistance index (Ri), no statistically significant differences were found between children in the control group and patients with stage 1 chronic kidney disease.

The absence of statistically significant differences in the resistance index (Ri) between the control group and patients at stage 1 of chronic kidney disease (CKD) indicates low information content of this indicator for early diagnosis of CKD. At the same time, all children with stages 3-4 of CKD showed a decrease in the resistance index (Ri) ($p < 0.05$).

Definitely, changes in the pulsatility index (Pi) were found in patients of the control group (1.06 ± 0.22) compared to patients in the remission stage of chronic inflammatory kidney disease (CIKD) (0.66 ± 0.19), $p < 0.001$. However, no statistically significant differences in the pulsatility index (Pi) were found at different stages of CKD: 0.66 ± 0.19 at the remission stage of CIKD, 0.61 ± 0.14 and 0.57 ± 0.09 at the active stage of CIKD, respectively, $p > 0.05$.

Statistically significant differences in the systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D) were established between children of the control group and patients at different stages of chronic inflammatory kidney disease (CIKD). With the onset of signs of CID progression, an increase in the systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D) is noted, which allows using this indicator as a tool for early diagnosis and prognosis of CKD progression in children.

According to echographic parameters in the color Doppler (CD) and duplex scanning (DS) modes, the most informative for diagnosing the initial stages of chronic kidney disease are systolic blood flow velocity (Vs), diastolic blood flow velocity (Vd) and systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D). No statistically significant differences ($p > 0.001$) were found in the values of the resistance index (Ri) and pulsatility index (Pi) between the control group and children at the stage of clinical remission.

It is important to suggest that statistically significant differences in the systolic-diastolic ratio (S/D) were found between children in the control group and patients at different stages of chronic inflammatory kidney disease (CID) ($p < 0.05$). With increasing stage of CKD, an increase in the S/D ratio was noted, which makes this indicator useful for early diagnosis and assessment of the progression of CKD in children.

Conclusions. By summarizing it should be suggested that the use of ultrasound examination made it possible to identify specific features of glomerulonephritis in children, both acute and chronic. These methods have demonstrated high information content, especially in differentiating the stages of the disease and assessing fibrous changes in the kidneys. The data obtained confirm the possibility of using non-invasive methods as an important tool for monitoring the condition of children with glomerulonephritis.

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